

Supplementary Figure S3. Neuronal cell death is not prominent in heads of 25-day-old *Adar*^{5G1} mutant flies. (A) TUNEL staining to detect apoptotic cells in head sections from 25-day-old *Adar*^{5G1} mutant flies stained with DAPI to detect nuclei. TUNEL-positive nuclei are not detected in neurons. However TUNEL-positive nuclei are conspicuous in head fat bodies of 25-day-old *Adar*^{5G1} mutant flies (boxed area in A). (B) Magnification of area boxed in A. (C) Haematoxylin and eosin stained section serial to A, white box indicates fat body tissue. (D) Magnification of area boxed in C. (E, F) Images show representative 6 micron thick haematoxylin and eosin stained sections through mushroom body calyces (left panels, (63X)) and retinas (right panels, 40X) of 30-day *Adar*^{5G1}; *Cha* > *UAS-p35*. Scale bars: 20μm